

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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THE IMPACT OF THE "FLIPPED CLASSROOM" MODEL ON LANGUAGE LEARNING

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15178958>

Abstract. *This article is devoted to the exploration of language learning within the framework focusing specifically on the utilization of "Flipped classroom" model. The origin, advantageous features and challenges can be faced of applying this model in the learning process are given with clear explanation. Different scientists' opinions about this method are presented. It observes how this approach empowers learners to engage in their language acquisition journey by learning theoretically about new theme outside the classroom and participating actively in-class-activities. This is the main difference between Flipped Classroom model and traditional way of teaching. Many studies that are carried out by researchers to analyse the impact of the FC model on language learning showed that there were noticeable improvements in the results of students. The problems encountered in this model, however, are categorized under three main titles: Motivation, Content, and Learning.*

Keywords: *flipped classroom model, traditional learning, motivation, teaching environment, innovative approach, in-class activities.*

Introduction

The use of the flipped classroom as an alternative to the traditional learning environments has been increasingly attracting the attention of researchers and educators. The advancement in technological tools such as interactive videos, interactive in-class activities, and video conference systems paves the way for the widespread use of flipped classrooms (Johnston, 2017). It is even asserted that the flipped classroom, which is used to create effective teaching environments at schools, is the best model for using technology in education (Hamdan, McKnight, McKnight, & Arfstrom, 2013). Studies about "Flipped Classroom" model appears in different fields of subject areas including engineering, sociology, humanities, mathematics education and English composition.

What is The "Flipped Classroom" Model?

Understanding the "**Flipped Classroom**" Model: The Flipped Classroom model is an innovative approach to education where traditional teaching methods are

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reversed. Instead of receiving theoretical instruction in class and doing exercises at home, students first learn new concepts independently through videos, texts, or interactive materials. Then, during class time, they engage in practical activities, discussions, and collaborative work to reinforce their learning.

For some the flipped classroom has become synonymous with **active learning**. There are many ways to incorporate active learning into your courses, and the flipped classroom is but one of those methods. A flipped classroom is structured around the idea that lecture or direct instruction is not the best use of class time. Instead students encounter information before class, freeing class time for activities that involve higher order thinking.

Impacts of the FC on Student Learning

In recent studies, the impacts of the FC Model on student performance, engagement, learning outcomes, and motivation have been investigated. Studies have shown that the FC approach enhances student's **learning performance** (Baepler, Walker, & Driessen, 2014; Davies et al., 2013; Janotha, 2016; Sun & Wu, 2016; Talley & Scherer, 2013), produces **enhanced learning outcomes** (Chen Hsieh, Wu, & Marek, 2017) and **increases student motivation** (Yilmaz, 2017).

Although most of the research suggests that the FC Model positively impacts students' learning, there are also studies which have not revealed anticipated positive effects. For example, Smallhorn (2017) did not find an observable increase in students' academic achievement. In another study conducted by Kim et al. (2014), they stated that there was no evidence that the FC Model contributed to increased student grades.

Content and the Procedure

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The necessary learning environments were designed for both groups to carry out the treatment. The general features of these learning environments are shown in Figure 1 (*Emine Cabi, PhD at Başkent University, 2018, July*).

Figure 1(*Emine Cabi, PhD at Başkent University, 2018, July*). *Features of learning environments for experimental group (flipped classroom) and control group (traditional learning).*

Discussion

Benefits of the Flipped Classroom Model in Language Learning

- **Personalized learning** – Students progress at their own pace and revisit materials as needed.
- **Increased communication and interactivity** – More class time is spent practicing speaking, listening, and engaging in real conversations.
- **Enhanced independent learning skills** – Students become more self-reliant and proactive in acquiring knowledge.

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▪ **Stronger teacher-student interaction** – Teachers act as facilitators, guiding students through interactive learning experiences.

▪ **Integration of digital tools** – Online resources such as YouTube videos, podcasts, and language-learning apps improve engagement and retention.

What are the problems you have encountered in FC Model?

Although a flipped classroom has many benefits, there can be **drawbacks** to the approach. With this style, teachers often utilize items like videos or other Internet-based research for the preparation work. This can be problematic for students who do not have *regular Internet access* outside of the classroom.

Teachers also spend more time preparing than those who run a traditional classroom, at least in the beginning. It can be tricky to figure out the *right balance of instruction and in-class activities*. Finally, teachers may deal with *student engagement issues*, such as students who are unwilling to complete the preparation work for class, defeating the purpose of the flipped classroom model.

Conclusion

The Flipped Classroom model is a highly effective method for language learning as it promotes *independent study* and *maximizes classroom interaction*. With the continued advancement of digital learning tools, this approach is likely to become even more widespread in the future. In addition, flipping the classroom enables participants to experience a deeper level of learning and feel more engaged during training sessions, because of the interactive, responsive and personal approach.

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